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ANTIOXIDANT STATUS IN ARTHROTIC ARTHRITIS

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Abstract: *The work included a comprehensive laboratory examination of patients with different stages of knee osteoarthritis. The patterns of metabolic disorders in patients with osteoarthritis in the form of activation of the prooxidant system and inhibition of the enzymatic link of antioxidant protection were revealed. It was shown that the degree of oxidative stress clearly correlates with the severity of clinical manifestations of osteoarthritis. The most clinically significant blood parameters for laboratory diagnostics of this pathology were identified, such as aliphatic aldehyde groups of oxidized proteins and paraoxanase activity.*

Key words: *osteoarthritis, prooxidant system, antioxidant system, oxidative modification of proteins, free radical oxidation of lipids, superoxide dismutase, catalase, myeloperoxidase, paraoxanase.*

Relevance. The human antioxidant system (AOC) is a system that blocks the formation of highly active free radicals, i.e. reactive oxygen species. Under normal physiological conditions, small amounts of oxygen are constantly converted to superoxide anions, hydrogen peroxide and hydroxyl radicals. Excessive production of these radicals is a damage factor, the compensatory mechanism of which is the antioxidant system. Determination of the total antioxidant status helps the clinician to further assess the state of the body observed and its potential protective reserves for certain physiological and pathological conditions.

The human antioxidant system (AOS) is a system that blocks the formation of highly active free radicals, i.e. reactive oxygen species. Under normal physiological conditions, small amounts of oxygen are constantly converted into superoxide anions, hydrogen peroxide and hydroxyl radicals. Excessive production of these radicals is a factor in damage, the compensatory mechanism of which is the antioxidant system. Determining the general antioxidant status helps the clinician to more deeply assess the condition of the body, observed and its potential protective reserves in certain physiological and pathological conditions (1,2,3,4,5,6,7). The importance of studying the pathogenesis of osteoarthritis (OA) is due to the prevalence of the disease -

epidemiological studies show that 10-12% of the population of all ages suffers from it, including 50% of people over 60 years old (1,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15). According to WHO forecasts, OA will become the fourth leading cause of disability in women and the eighth in men in the next 10-15 years [1,16,17,18,19]. It is believed that the universal mechanism of OA pathogenesis is the imbalance between the processes of synthesis and degradation of cartilage components. The key role in this is given, firstly, to the disruption of the functioning of chondrocytes, which begin to produce "inferior" low-molecular matrix proteins, and, secondly, to biochemical disorders, changes in the activity of enzymes in the articular tissue.

The mechanism of formation and development of these leading links in the pathogenesis of OA is still not fully understood. At the same time, specific OA processes have been studied much better than non-specific reactions, and it is the latter that are primarily protective, formed by evolution. The development of OA is based on such typical pathological processes as tissue degeneration, inflammation and stress, the body's systemic response to which includes the activation of free radical destabilization of cells, both in the area of local damage and far beyond it. At the same time, the balance of the prooxidant (POS) and antioxidant (AOS) systems is a prerequisite for health, an indicator of the adaptive and protective capabilities of the body.

The aim was to study metabolic parameters at the systemic and local levels in arthrotic arthritis depending on the age of patients.

Materials and methods 96 patients with arthrotic arthritis who underwent inpatient treatment at the clinic of the National Center for Rehabilitation and Prosthetics of Persons with Disabilities under the National Agency for Social Protection under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan were examined.

Results and conclusion. The results of studies showed that in patients with AA of both age groups in synovial fluid, the pattern of changes in the level of SOD was different. In young patients, we also see a 1.4-fold decrease in SOD (up to 638.3 ± 126.2 pg/ml) compared to the control group (897.5 ± 61.8 pg/ml). And in middle-aged patients, we see the opposite picture - an increase in the level of TRD by 1.2 times compared to the control group.

In AA patients in both age groups, we see an increase in MDA. In synovial fluid, this process was less intense and was higher than the control group (1.64 ± 0.46 $\mu\text{mol/ml}$) in young patients by 3.9 times (6.38 ± 1.13 $\mu\text{mol/ml}$), in middle-aged patients by 4.5 times (7.43 ± 1.27 $\mu\text{mol/ml}$).

Conclusions: The revealed reduced levels of SOD and increased levels of MDA lead to the accumulation of ROS, which enhances the processes of POL and increases the level of MDA, which creates a vicious circle of oxidative damage that accelerates the

progression of arthrotic arthritis. Although at the systemic level, the mechanism of oxidative stress disturbance is general, at the local level, each age period is characterized by a specific mechanism of action of SOD. Metabolic and oxidative changes play a key role in the pathogenesis of arthrotic arthritis, increasing inflammation and degradation of articular tissue. An in-depth study of these processes can contribute to the development of new therapeutic approaches aimed at reducing oxidative stress and correcting metabolic disorders to improve the quality of life of patients with arthrotic arthritis.

Literature

1. Bobaev N. M. Osteoarthritis and osteoporosis bilan birga kelishida khavf omillaring hususiyatlari : a scientific publication / N. M. Bobaev, M. Z. Rizamukhamedova, S. M. Muammadiyeva // Infection, immunity and Pharmacology : a scientific and practical journal. - 2019. - N 3. - C. 9-14.
2. Dadabayeva N. A. The role of metabolic syndrome and adipocytokines in the pathogenesis of osteoarthritis / N. A. Dadabayeva, H. T. Mirakhmedova, N. A. Ramazanova. - Text : direct // Bulletin of the Tashkent Medical Academy. - 2023.- N 5. - C. 58-60.
3. Konkova O.A., Nazarenko S.A., Umerenkova S.A., Shapovalova O.N. Inflammatory theories of osteoarthritis: aging of the immune system as a trigger factor in the pathogenesis of osteoarthritis//Alley of Science. 2019. t.1. № 3 (30). C. 143-146.
4. Kravtsov V.I., Sivordova L.E., Polyakova Yu.V., Zavodovsky B.V. Lipid imbalance in patients with osteoarthritis and its role in the pathogenesis of the disease// In the book: Days of Rheumatology in St. Petersburg - 2017. Collection of abstracts of the Congress with international participation. Edited by V.I. Mazurov. 2017. pp. 121-123.
5. Khamdamov I.B. Improving tactical approaches in the treatment of hernias of the anterior abdominal wall in women of fertile age // New day in medicine. Bukhara, 2022.-№10(48)- pp. 338-342.
6. Khamdamov I.B. Morphofunctional features of the abdominal press in women of reproductive age // New day in medicine. Bukhara, 2022.-№3(41)- pp. 223-227.
7. Khamdamova M.T. Ultrasound features of three-dimensional echography in assessing the condition of the endometrium and uterine cavity in women of the first period of middle age using intrauterine contraceptives // Biology va tibbyot muammolari. - Samarkand, 2020. - No. 2 (118). - P.127-131.
8. Khamdamova M. T. Anthropometric characteristics of the physical status of women in the first and second period of middle age // A new day in medicine. Tashkent, 2020. - № 1 (29). - C.98-100.

9. Khamdamova M.T., Zhaloldinova M.M., Khamdamov I.B. The state of nitric oxide in blood serum in patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis // *New day in medicine*. Bukhara, 2023. - No. 5 (55). - pp. 638-643.
10. Khamdamova M.T., Zhaloldinova M.M., Khamdamov I.B. The value of ceruloplasmin and copper in blood serum in women wearing copper-containing intrauterine device // *New day in medicine*. Bukhara, 2023. - No. 6 (56). - pp. 2-7.
11. Khamdamova M. T. Bleeding when wearing intrauterine contraceptives and their relationship with the nitric oxide system // *American journal of pediatric medicine and health sciences* Volume 01, Issue 07, 2023 ISSN (E): 2993-2149. P.58-62
12. Khamdamova M. T. The state of local immunity in background diseases of the cervix // *Eurasian journal of medical and natural sciences Innovative Academy Research Support Center*. Volume 3 Issue 1, January 2023 ISSN 2181-287X P.171-175.
13. Khamdamova M.T., Khasanova M.T. Various mechanisms of pathogenesis of endometrial hyperplasia in postmenopausal women (literature review) // *New day in medicine*. Bukhara. 2023. - No. 8 (58). - pp. 103-107.
14. Khamdamova M.T. Reproductive Health of Women Using Copper-Containing Intrauterine Contraception // *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical* Volume 28 January 2024, ISSN: 2795-7624 .www.geniusjournals.org P. 39-45.
15. Khamdamov I.B. Advantages Of Laparoscopic Hernioplasty in Obesity Women of Fertile Age // *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical* Volume 28 January 2024, ISSN: 2795-7624 .www.geniusjournals.org P. 33-38.
16. Khamdamova M. T., Khasanova M.T. Genetic mechanisms of development of endometrial hyperplastic processes in women in menopausal age // *American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences* 2025.- №15(2): P.372-375 DOI: 10.5923/j.ajmms.20251502.22
17. Khamdamova M. T., Akramova D.E. The problem of pelvic organ prolapse in women in modern gynecology // *American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences* 2025, 15(2): 483-486 DOI: 10.5923/j.ajmms.20251502.47
18. Khamdamova M. T., Umidova Nigora Nabi kizi. Endometriosis and women's reproductive health // *American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences* 2025; 15(2): 407-410 DOI:10.5923/j.ajmms.20251502.28
19. Khamdamov B. Z. et al. The role and place laser photodynamic therapy in prevention postoperative complication at treatment of diabetic foot syndrome // *Applied Sciences: challenges and solutions*. – 2015. – C. 27-31.